

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *AMARANTHUS GANGETICUS*. PART I. THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS

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The physical and chemical constants of the oil obtained from the seeds of *amaranthus gangeticus* have been determined and the saturated and the unsaturated fatty acids obtained by the saponification of the oil have been examined.

Amaranthus Gangeticus is a variety of amaranthus of the family 'Amaranthaceae', indigenous to South Travancore. Although this plant is very common and yields a considerable crop of a small seed little information is available regarding the nature of the fatty oils which might be obtained from this source. The only published work is on the oil from the allied species *A. Rotroflexus* (Christensen and Muller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2272).

EXPERIMENTAL

6 Kg of the seeds were collected under the personal supervision of the authors, and the dried sample was crushed and repeatedly extracted with petroleum ether (b. p. 50—60°) in the Soxhlet. The petrol was distilled off and the resulting light yellow oil when dried, weighed 360 g., yield 6%.

TABLE I

Physical and Chemical constants of the Oil.

Sp. gravity (20°)	0.9021	Mean M. W. of saturated acids	264.5
Refractive Index (Abbe) (28°)	1.4733	Iodine value of unsaturated acids	106.4
Iodine value (Wijze)	76.3	Iodine value of saturated acids	2.6
Saponification value	175.6	Acid value	12.4
Unsaturated acids (basis of oil)	71.12%	Acetyl value	19.7
Saturated acids (basis of oil)	22.88%	Reichert Meisel value	0.71
Mean M. W. of unsaturated acids	283.0	Polenske number	0.50
		Unsaponifiable matter	2.6%

The oil was saponified in the usual manner, the unsaponifiable matter extracted with ether and the fatty acids were liberated. The mixture of the fatty acids was then separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by the Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 12, 806) and their percentage and constants found (*vide* Table I).

Examination of the Unsaturated Acids.

About 3 g. of the liquid were oxidised with alkaline permanganate at 0°. From the precipitated oxidised acids 9:10-dihydroxystearic acid (mixed m. p. with authentic specimen, 132°) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 156°) have been obtained thus showing the presence of mainly oleic and linolic acids in the oil.

The quantitative estimation was done by the method, adopted by Jamieson and Baughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1198). A known weight of the unsaturated acids was dissolved in 150 c.c of dry ether and treated with excess of bromine at -10° to -5°. On standing at this temperature for a long time no insoluble bromide separated showing the absence of linolinic acid. The excess of bromine was removed with thiosulphate and the ether evaporated off. The residue from the above was taken up with about 200 c.c. of dry petroleum ether and kept overnight. Linolic tetrabromide separated

as fine glistening star-shaped needles, which were filtered off, washed and dried (m. p. 111°). On concentrating the mother-liquor, a further crop of tetrabromide was obtained which was added to the first and the total weight determined. Finally the petroleum ether filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the bromine content of the residue determined.

TABLE II

Percentage of the components.

Acids.	In unsaturated acids	In mixed acids	In original oil
Oleic	61.54	46.5	43.7
Linolic	38.46	29.1	27.3

Examination of the Saturated Acids.

The mixture of the saturated acids was converted into their methyl esters; and 16 g. of the mixed esters were fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. The saponification equivalents of the various fractions were found out. The acids were liberated from the different fractions and characterised by their melting points and preparation of derivatives.

TABLE III

B. p. at 5 mm. pressure.	Wt.	Sapon. equiv.	B. p. at 5 mm. pressure.	Wt.	Sapon. equiv.
S ₁ 148–152° (nearly constant)	11.6 g.	271.0	S ₂ 160–165° (gradually rising above 180°)	1.05 g.	290.0
S ₂ 152–155° (rose to 180°C)	1.1 g.	272.1	S ₃ Residue	1.2 g.	

As will be seen about 85.6% came over in the first two fractions. The saponification equivalent of S₁ and S₂ (271 and 272.1 respectively) correspond to that of methyl palmitate. The acid was regenerated from S₁ and S₂ mixed together and recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 62° (anilide, m. p. 87°). Anilide of palmitic acid melts at 87.5°. Hence the acid is palmitic and fractions S₁ and S₂ contain palmitic ester. Fraction S₃ had a saponification equivalent 290, which is nearly equal to that of methyl stearate (297). It melted between 35° and 36.5°. The acid was generated and found to melt at 70° (m. p. of steric acid, 72°). Hence the acid is stearic and S₃ contains mainly stearic ester. Calculations on the basis of saponification equivalents give palmitic acid (20.84%) stearic acid (2.16%) in the original oil.

The unsaponifiable portion yields a needle-shaped crystalline sterol which is under examination.

The seeds after extraction of the oil have been successively extracted with other solvents and we have been able to get crystalline products from the ethyl acetate and alcoholic extracts; these are also under examination.

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